

MODELING OF VOID EFFECT ON MATRIX-DOMINATED STRENGTH OF CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) applying epoxy resin for their matrix are increasingly used for high-performance structural components that require high specific strength and/or stiffness like aerospace applications. Such CFRPs are typically used in the form of laminates, which are usually manufactured using an autoclave to apply curing conditions specified for the matrix material systems. If the curing conditions are not within specified tolerances, voids, a typical kind of manufacturing defects of CFRP laminates, can be formed in the matrix. Authors performed tests previously to investigate the effects of voids on three types of matrix-dominated strengths of CFRP laminates, i.e. transverse tensile strength (TTS), inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS), and inter-laminar tensile strength (ILTS), of which loading directions are different relative to the fiber directions. The test results showed that these strengths decreased as void volume fractions, V_v , increased and the ratios of strength reductions to V_v differed depending on the loading directions. In the present study, statistical features of void locations and dimensions were investigated more in detail by image analysis on the X-ray computed tomography (CT). Based on the analyzed statistics, the stress concentration effects were estimated. A model based on Weibull's weakest link theory was proposed to account for the effect of V_v on the reduction in TTS, a typical case of matrix dominated strengths. The model could fit well to the test results by choosing the parameters properly.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are now widely used for high-performance structural components like aerospace applications that require both high structural performance, such as strength and stiffness, and weight reduction. Since CFRPs consist of carbon fibers and synthetic polymeric resin, they are inhomogeneous materials having strongly anisotropic mechanical properties such as tensile strength and modulus much higher in fiber direction than those in transverse directions. In the case of CFRP applying epoxy, i.e. typical thermosetting resin for its matrix, it is hence usually used in the form of laminate fabricated by stacking prepregs in a pre-determined arrangement to include intended fiber directions and having resultant material properties as a laminated part. Such CFRP laminates are usually fabricated using an autoclave to apply elevated temperature and pressure conditions specified for the material system to cure the epoxy resin. Although there are some causes of void formation like moisture dissolved in resin [1] or air entrapped during lay-up or during impregnation of resin in pre-preg processing [2], many of voids can be eliminated by applying elevated pressures in autoclave, and CFRP laminates can be fabricated with high internal quality.

Even with autoclave curing process having such benefits, if the curing conditions are not within the specified tolerances in the case like manufacturing process is not applied or controlled properly for some reason, voids, a typical kind of manufacturing defects of CFRP laminates, can be formed in the matrix. Previous researches revealed that voids significantly reduced the matrix-dominated strengths, such as transverse tension, axial compression, flexure, and shear [3]. Many of those previous researches dealing with the effect of voids on the strength of CFRP laminates were focused on the

relationship between void volume fraction, V_v , and the strength in respective fracture modes. Those researches revealed that voids affect mechanical properties of CFRP laminates, such as modulus of elasticity, and degrade compressive strength in fiber direction, tensile and compressive strengths in transverse direction, flexure strength, and interlaminar shear strength [4-10]. It has also been demonstrated that the effect of voids on these strength reduction is increased in accordance with increase in V_v .

Authors performed tests previously [11], as shown later in Figure 3, to investigate the effects of voids on three types of matrix-dominated strengths of CFRP laminates, i.e. transverse tensile strength (TTS), inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS), and inter-laminar tensile strength (ILTS), of which loading directions are different relative to the fiber directions. Specimens were cut from laminates including voids prepared by intentionally changing curing conditions. These strengths decreased as void volume fractions, V_v , increased. The ratios of strength reductions to V_v differed depending on the loading directions. Microscopic observations of void shapes by X-ray computed tomography (CT) for the samples taken from the same laminates as those tests revealed that the void were generally long and flat cylindrical or ellipsoidal shapes of which major axes were parallel to the fiber directions. It was hence considered that the strength reduction ratios to V_v were basically in relation to the stress concentrations around voids, which have certain relationship with the fiber directions. However, theoretical modeling of strength reductions in accordance with increase in V_v was not investigated.

In this study, statistical features of void locations and dimensions were investigated more in detail by image analysis on the X-ray CT. Based on the analyzed statistics, the stress concentration effects were estimated. A model based on Weibull's weakest link theory was proposed to account for the effect of V_v on the reduction in TTS, a typical case of matrix dominated strengths. The model could fit well to the test results by choosing the parameters properly.

2 STATISTICAL ANALYSES ON THE SIZES AND SHAPES OF VOIDS MEASURED BY X-RAY CT OBSERVATION

Detailed statistical analyses were performed on the three-dimensional (3D) CT images obtained in the previous study by the authors [11]. The locations and sizes, i.e. lengths along respective coordinates, of voids were measured by CT image analysis. Figure 1 shows the definition of the coordinates for these measurements. The statistical features of the spatial distributions, sizes and shapes (aspect ratios) of voids were then investigated.

Figure 1: Definition of coordinates for the measurement of void sizes and locations.

It was clarified that voids were uniformly distributed in the inter-laminar resin-rich regions in CFRP laminates. It was also revealed that the sizes and aspect ratios of voids had log-normal distributions. Figure 2 shows the comparison of measured and generated statistic parameters, i.e. mean,

variance and root mean square (RMS), of aspect ratio A/B , as an example. The “measured” parameters were calculated from the measured void sizes. The “generated” parameters were calculated from the void sizes randomly generated assuming log-normal distributions. The measured parameters thus agreed well to the generated parameters, i.e. log-normal distributions. It is also shown that the parameters of those distributions have no significant dependence on V_v .

Figure 2: Comparison of measured and generated statistical parameters for void size distribution – aspect ratio A/B .

3 MODELING OF STRENGTH REDUCTION CAUSED BY STRESS CONCENTRATION AROUND VOIDS

3.1 TTS test result

Figure 3 shows the test results of TTS and modulus with respect to V_v performed in the previous study by the authors [11]. Unidirectional carbon/epoxy UTS50/#135 prepreg (Toho Tenax, 180°C cure type) was used to prepare the specimens for these tests. Curing conditions were intentionally changed from the specified one for this material system to prepare six laminates with respective levels of void volume fractions, V_v , while the curing condition was as specified to prepare one laminate without voids, i.e. $V_v=0\%$. Stacking sequence was unidirectional $[0_{24}]$. Specimens were cut out from these laminates.

Figure 3: V_v vs Transverse tensile strength (TTS) and coefficient of variation (CV) test result [11].

The test results were normalized using the averages of the test results for $V_v=0\%$. The reduction in TTS was increased proportionally to the increase in V_v , and reached nearly 30% for the largest void volume fractions, $V_v=7.1\%$.

3.2 Size effect of strength in Weibull's theory

Brittle fracture feature was observed in the tests for TTS referred in the previous section. Weibull's weakest link theory was hence assumed as a basis for the modeling of strength reduction due to void existence. Risk of rupture in Weibull's theory is written as:

$$B = \left(\frac{\sigma_R}{\sigma_0} \right)^m V^{eff} = \int_V \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m dV \quad (1)$$

Considering two materials, 1 and 2, having the same Weibull parameter but different effective volumes, V_1^{eff} and V_2^{eff} , and defining representative strengths, σ_1 and σ_2 , for respective materials where $B=1$, the size effect of strength is obtained as equation (2). m is the Weibull shape parameter for these materials.

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \left(\frac{V_1^{eff}}{V_2^{eff}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (2)$$

3.3 Modeling of stress concentration and strength reduction caused by void

As mentioned above in Section 2, no clear dependence on V_v was observed for the sizes and aspect ratios of voids, which affect the stress concentration factors around voids. It was hence considered that not one or a few voids having specific features but the sum of the effects of stress concentrations around voids could contribute the strength reductions in accordance with increase in V_v . Risk of rupture of a material including voids can be defined as equation (3) derived from equation (1) and accounting for the stress concentration factor α around voids.

$$\begin{aligned} B &\approx \int_V \left\{ \frac{\alpha \sigma(\mathbf{x})}{\sigma_0} \right\}^m dV \\ &= \int_V \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m dV + \sum_i \int_{V_i} (\alpha_i^m - 1) \left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_0} \right)^m dV_i \\ &\equiv B_0 + B^* \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where

$$B_0 = \int_V \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0} \right)^m dV \quad (4)$$

$$B^* = \sum_i \int_{V_i} (\alpha_i^m - 1) \left(\frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_0} \right)^m dV_i \quad (5)$$

B_0 is the risk of rupture of a material without voids. B^* is the increment in risk of rupture due to void existence in the material.

Similarly to the previous section, considering two materials, 1 and 2, having the same Weibull-like parameter m but different void volume fractions, V_{v1} and V_{v2} , and defining representative strengths, σ_1 and σ_2 where $B=1$, a model similar to the size effect of strengths shown in equation (2) was proposed as described in equation (6).

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \left(\frac{1 + \beta V_{v1} a_1}{1 + \beta V_{v2} a_2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \quad (6)$$

where

$$a = \sum_i (\alpha_i^m - 1) \frac{V_{void,i}}{V_{void}} \quad (7)$$

α_i is the stress concentration factor for a void i of which volume is $V_{void,i}$. V_{void} is the sum of the volume of all voids in a material. Therefore, α becomes the weighted average of stress concentration factors considering respective volumes of voids. Again, since no clear dependence on V_v was observed for the sizes and aspect ratios of voids, α 's calculated by equation (7) result in similar values, i.e. $\alpha_1 \cong \alpha_2$, even for different void volume fractions. m is usually much larger than 1. Equation (8) is hence obtained by omitting the first terms 1 in both denominator and numerator in equation (6).

$$\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_2} = \left(\frac{V_{v1}}{V_{v2}} \right)^{-\frac{1}{m}} \quad (8)$$

Figure 4 shows the relationship between V_v and mean strengths from TTS test results. The results of equations (6) and (8) are also shown in this figure. As a result to fit these equations to the test results, $\alpha=2$ and $m=9.13$ was obtained for equation (6) and $m=9.13$ and 29.8 was obtained for equation (8). Thus, equation (6) with these parameters can fit to the test results. And this condition is close to the equation (8) with $m=9.13$, which is the case of strong stress concentration effect.

Figure 4: Relationship between void volume fractions and mean strengths for transverse tensile strength (TTS) of CFRP.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Analyses for statistical features of sizes and spatial distributions of voids showed that they follow log-normal distributions that are not dependent on void volume fractions, V_v .

Based on the analyzed statistics, a model based on Weibull's weakest link theory and considering stress concentration effects was proposed to account for the effect of voids on TTS. The result showed the proposed model could fit to the test results by choosing parameters appropriately.

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